

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of DL-Methionine by Potassium Bromate in Sulphuric Acid Medium

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In continuation of our work on the oxidation of methionine¹, one of the sulphur containing optically active essential amino acids, we now report the mechanism of its oxidation in H₂SO₄ medium by potassium bromate both in absence and in presence of bromide ion.

Results and Discussion

The reaction between methionine and bromate ion was carried out at 30° in 0.2 mol dm⁻³ sulphuric acid medium. It was reported earlier that in the oxidation of many substrates by BrO₃⁻, molecular bromine will be produced from *in situ* formation of Br₂ ion. So in this investigation also there may be a possibility of oxidation of methionine by both bromate and bromine. Hence, the reaction was carried out in presence of mercuric acetate which traps Br₂ as a complex such that *in situ* formation of Br₂ can be prevented. However, even at 100-fold excess of Hg^{II} no limiting rate was obtained. Also, in presence of a large excess of Hg^{II} the rate was found to decrease with increase in methionine concentration. It is therefore suspected that there might be complexation between Hg^{II} and methionine. This was verified through mixing 1.5 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ methionine and 1.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ Hg(OAc)₂ in 1.0 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ medium and scanning the absorption spectrum of the mixture; an increase in absorbance was observed in the uv region indicating complexation between Hg^{II} and methionine. The formation of a complex through the sulphur atom of methionine and Hg^{II} was also indicated by earlier workers in the microdetermination of peptides and amino acids².

In view of these observations kinetic runs were carried out in presence of a 20-fold excess of cadmium(II) which also acts as a bromide ion scavenger³ but does
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not form a complex with methionine. A limiting rate was observed when cadmium(II) concentration was in 20-fold excess to that of methionine. Hence, in all the kinetic runs carried out in absence of bromide, a 20-fold excess of [Cd^{II}] was maintained.

Known amounts of bromate was allowed to react completely with a known excess of methionine at 30° in presence of a large excess of Cd^{II} in 0.2 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ medium and the unreacted methionine was estimated iodimetrically. The stoichiometry was found to correspond to the equation

Product analysis : A 0.4 mol dm⁻³ NaHCO₃ solution was added to the reaction mixture (after completion of the reaction) with vigorous stirring followed by dropwise addition of benzoyl chloride solution until precipitation was completed. The precipitate was confirmed to be *N*-benzoylmethionine sulphoxide, a derivative of methionine sulphoxide, and was identified by its melting point¹.

When kinetic runs were carried out isolating BrO₃⁻ by keeping [methionine] in large excess, the plots of log (T_∞ - T_t) vs time were found to be linear beyond two half-lives of the reaction, indicating the order with respect to BrO₃⁻ to be unity. Further, when [BrO₃⁻] was varied from 2.5 × 10⁻⁴ to 30.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ the pseudo-first order rate constant (*k*) was found to remain constant, confirming first order dependence on [BrO₃⁻] (Table 1). The order with respect to methionine was determined by carrying out kinetic runs in 0.2 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ keeping the concentration of bro-

TABLE 1 – DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON $[\text{BrO}_3^-]$, $[\text{Met}]$ AND $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ IN PRESENCE OF $\text{Cd}(\text{OAc})_2$: $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ AT 30°

$\times 10^4$ $[\text{BrO}_3^-]$ mol dm^{-3}	$\times 10^3$ $[\text{Met}]$ mol dm^{-3}	$\times 10^2$ $[\text{Cd}(\text{OAc})_2]$ mol dm^{-3}	$[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ mol dm^{-3}	$\times 10^3$ k' s^{-1}
2.5	15.0	4.0	—	1.06
5.0	15.0	4.0	—	1.08
10.0	15.0	4.0	—	1.08
20.0	15.0	4.0	—	1.06
25.0	15.0	4.0	—	1.07
30.0	15.0	4.0	—	1.06
5.0	7.5	1.0	—	0.55
5.0	10.0	1.0	—	0.69
5.0	15.0	1.0	—	1.08
5.0	20.0	1.0	—	1.39
5.0	25.0	1.0	—	1.78
5.0	15.0	1.0	0.20	1.07
5.0	15.0	1.0	0.25	1.32
5.0	15.0	1.0	0.30	1.60
5.0	15.0	1.0	0.35	2.11
5.0	15.0	1.0	0.40	2.40

mate ion constant but varying that of methionine from 7.5×10^{-3} to $25.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The results (Table 1) reveal that the reaction rate increases with increase in the concentration of methionine. When the rate constants were plotted against the concentration of methionine, a linear plot passing through origin was obtained, indicating an order of unity in [methionine].

In order to study the effect of acid concentration on the observed pseudo-first order rate constants, kinetic runs were carried out at various $[\text{H}^+]$ varying from 0.2 to 0.5 mol dm^{-3} , keeping the concentration of the reactants constant. The pseudo-first order rate constants were found to increase with increasing $[\text{H}^+]$. Further, the plot of k' vs $[\text{H}^+]^2$ was found to be linear passing through origin indicating second order dependence on $[\text{H}^+]$ (Fig. 1).

The effect of ionic strength on the pseudo-first order rate constant was studied in $0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$, varying the ionic strength from 0.2 to 1.0 mol dm^{-3} using NaClO_4 . The rate constants were found

unaffected by the ionic strength of the medium.

In order to study the effect of bisulphate ion on the pseudo-first order rate constant, kinetic runs were carried out varying $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ from 0.2 to 0.4 mol dm^{-3} using NaHSO_4 and keeping the concentrations of other ions constant. The results (Table 1) indicate that increase in $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ causes an increase in the rate of the reaction.

Fig. 1. Plots of k' vs $[\text{H}^+]^2$: (A) $[\text{BrO}_3^-] = 5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Met}] = 1.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Cd}(\text{OAc})_2] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{temp} = 303 \text{ K}$; (B) $[\text{BrO}_3^-] = 5.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Br}^-] = 5.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Met}] = 1.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{temp} = 303 \text{ K}$.

The effect of temperature on the rate was studied by carrying out the reaction at 25 , 30 , 35 and 40° and the rate constants thus obtained were recorded in Table 2. The plot of $\log k'$ vs $1/T$ was linear, indicating that the reaction obeys Arrhenius temperature dependence. The energy of activation (E_a) and entropy of activation ($\Delta S^\ddagger$) calculated using linear least-squares method were found to be $58.2 \pm 5.90 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-83.7 \pm 19.3 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. Under the experimental conditions employed in the present investigation ($0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$) bromate exists mainly in the form of the protonated species HBrO_3 and H_2BrO_3^+ ⁵.

Methionine also exists in the form of the protonated species $\text{CH}_3\text{SCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{NH}_3^+)\text{COOH}$ (R-S- CH_3) to an extent of $> 98\%$. In view of these observations the following mechanism has been proposed:

where, R = (-CH₂CH₂CH(+NH₃)COOH). This mechanism leads to the rate equation,

$$\text{Rate} = -\frac{d[\text{BrO}_3^-]}{dt} = k [\text{R}-\text{S}-\text{CH}_3] [\text{H}_2\text{BrO}_3^+] \quad (6)$$

$$= k K_1 K_2 [\text{R}-\text{S}-\text{CH}_3] [\text{H}^+]^2 [\text{BrO}_3^-] \quad (7)$$

The rate equation explains the first order dependence of rate on [methionine] and [BrO₃⁻]. Further, equation (7) predicts the plot of *k'* (i.e. rate/[BrO₃⁻]) vs [H⁺]² should be linear passing through the origin. Experimentally such a plot is obtained (Fig. 1) supporting the proposed mechanism.

TABLE 2 – EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT (*k'*)

[BrO₃⁻] = 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, [Met] = 15.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³

Temp. (K)	× 10 ³ <i>k'</i> s ⁻¹	
	(A)	(B)
	[Cd(OAc) ₂] = 1.0 × 10 ⁻² mol dm ⁻³	[Br ⁻] = 5.0 × 10 ⁻² mol dm ⁻³
	[H ₂ SO ₄] = 0.2 mol dm ⁻³	[H ₂ SO ₄] = 0.1 mol dm ⁻³
298	0.80	2.05
303	1.08	2.92
308	1.75	4.26
313	2.34	5.11

Effect of [Bromide]: The effect of [Br⁻] on the rate of reaction was studied in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ medium in the absence of cadmium(II) and varying [Br⁻] from 5.0 × 10⁻³ to 5.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ using KBr. The rate of the reaction was found to increase with increase in [Br⁻] (Table 3). In presence of Br⁻, oxidation of methionine proceeds simultaneously by both bromate and molecular Br₂. Hence, the reaction was studied in presence of 100-fold excess of Br⁻, under which condition oxidation of methionine may be presumed to be proceeding mainly through molecular Br₂. The order with respect to methionine was studied in presence of 5.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ [Br⁻] and varying the [methionine] from 7.5 to 25.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ at 30° in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ medium. The pseudo-first order rate constants were found to be independent of [methionine], indicating zero order dependence on [methionine] (Table 3).

Ionic strength was found to have negligible effect on the rate of reaction but the rate was found to increase with increase in [H⁺]. Further, the plot of *k'* vs [H⁺]² was found to be a straight-line passing through the origin, indicating an order of 2 in [H⁺] (Fig. 1). The effect of temperature on rate was also studied in presence of Br⁻ at different temperatures 25, 30, 35 and 40° and the rate constants thus obtained are recorded in Table 2. The activation parameters determined

TABLE 3 – DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON [Br⁻] AND [Met]

[BrO₃⁻] = 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄] = 0.1 mol dm⁻³, Temp = 30°

× 10 ² [Br ⁻] mol dm ⁻³	× 10 ³ [Met] mol dm ⁻³	× 10 ³ <i>k'</i> s ⁻¹
0.5	15.0	0.36
1.0	15.0	0.62
1.5	15.0	0.92
2.5	15.0	1.40
3.5	15.0	1.96
4.0	15.0	2.24
5.0	15.0	2.76
5.0	7.5	2.76
5.0	10.0	2.80
5.0	15.0	2.78
5.0	20.0	2.76
5.0	25.0	2.82

from these rate constants were found to be $E_a = 48.6 \pm 4.6 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger = -141.9 \pm 15.2 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

In presence of excess Br the reactive species is presumed to be molecular Br_2 which reacts with the substrate in a fast step. The following mechanism may be proposed based on the experimental observations :

Alternatively, steps (9) and (10) may be represented as

This mechanism leads to the rate equation,

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 K_1 K_2 [\text{H}^+]^2 [\text{BrO}_3^-] [\text{Br}^-] \quad (13)$$

From equation (13) it may be seen that the rate is independent of [methionine] at high [Br⁻] and the plot of k_1 vs $[\text{H}^+]^2$ should be linear passing through origin. Exactly such a plot is obtained experimentally thus supporting the proposed mechanism.

Evidence for the fact that the formation of molecular bromine itself is rate-limiting in the oxidation of methionine by bromate in presence of excess of bromide is also furnished by the following observations.

(i) When the reaction is initiated with methionine, it is

completed almost instantaneously. Further, the oxidation of methionine by bromine water under similar conditions is also almost instantaneous. (ii) The rate constant for the formation of molecular bromine by bromate-bromide mixture ($360 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$) has been found to be in good agreement with that for the oxidation of methionine by bromate ($332 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$) under similar conditions.

In the oxidation of methionine by iodine^{6,7}, Cr^{VI} ^{4,8}, Ce^{IV} ⁹, V^{V} ⁹, hexacyanoferrate(III)¹⁰ and Fe^{III} in presence of 1,10-phenanthroline¹¹, the reaction proceeds upto sulphoxide stage only, whereas in the case of chloramine-B¹², bromamine-B¹³ and Mn^{II} ¹¹ the final product is sulphone. In all these oxidations, the electrophilic attack by the oxidant was reported to take place at sulphur site. In the present reaction also the site of attack is believed to be sulphur atom and the reaction proceeds through the formation of an intermediate between H_2BrO_3^+ and sulphur atom of methionine leading to the formation of sulphoxide as shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

The subsequent oxidation of methionine by Br^{III} and Br^{I} to the final Br^{I} stage takes place in fast steps.

Experimental

Potassium bromate (A.R., B.D.H.) was used as received. DL-Methionine (Himedia) was used and its strength determined by iodimetric method⁶. Cadmium acetate (A.R., B.D.H.) was used as a scavenger of bromide ion.

The kinetic runs were carried out at 30° in aqueous H_2SO_4 medium keeping [methionine] in large excess. The progress of the reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted bromate iodometrically at regular intervals of time. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k') determined from $\log(T_\infty - T_t)$ versus time plots were found to be reproducible within $\pm 3\%$.

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